

ISic1130

I.Sicily inscription 1130

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Soluntum

Place of origin (modern)

Solunto

Provenance

so-called 'Gymnasium'

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8809

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Πεζῶν τάξεις τρεῖς αἰ
2. στρατευσάμεναι ἐπὶ Ἀ
3. πολλωνίου Ἀπολλωνίου καὶ
4. οἱ αὐτοῦ ἔφηβοι Ἄνταλλον Ἄν
5. τάλλου τοῦ Ἀντάλλου Ὀρνι
6. χᾶν γυμνασιαρχήσαντα
7. εὐνοίας ἔνεκα

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492743

EDR 136430

EDCS 39102287

PHI 140615

PHI 175714

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